

Infrared and Thermal Studies of Dibenzyl Sulphoxide Complexes of Dioxouranium(II)

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Coordination compounds of dibenzyl sulphoxide (DBzSO) with UO_2X_2 ($X=Cl, Br, I, NO_3, NCS$ or CH_3COO) have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, molecular weight, conductance, infrared and TG data. Such study indicate the monomeric nature of the adducts $UO_2X_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$, where the UO_2^{II} is bonded to the oxygen atom of DBzSO ligand. Force constant and U-O bond distance have also been calculated.

SULPHOXIDE, with the general formula R_2SO ($R=$ alkyl or aryl) have large dipole moment ($\sim 4.0D$). They are excellent nucleophiles capable of coordinating to the metal ions, through either sulphur or oxygen¹. In recent years, a number of sulphoxide complexes of transition and non-transition metal ions are reported^{1,2}. Comparatively less is known about the compounds of dioxouranium(II) with sulphoxides³⁻¹². In all these complexes, sulphoxides coordinate UO_2^{II} through their oxygen atoms. In this paper, some details of ir and thermal studies of dibenzyl sulphoxide (DBzSO) complexes of dioxouranium(II) are given. There seems to be no prior reports on these complexes in the literature.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical grade. Uranyl nitrate, uranyl chloride and uranyl acetate were available commercially, while uranyl bromide was prepared from uranyl acetate by treating it with hydrobromic acid¹³. Uranyl iodide was obtained by treating uranyl nitrate with barium iodide in dry ether¹⁴. Uranyl thiocyanate was prepared by mixing an ethanolic solution of uranyl nitrate and potassium thiocyanate, when potassium nitrate was precipitated¹⁰. The ligand DBzSO (Merck) was used as such.

Preparation of complexes: All the complexes were obtained by the following general method. The uranyl salt (1 mmol) dissolved in acetone (25 ml) was mixed with ligand (2 mmol) in acetone (20 ml). After concentrating the solution by evaporation in dry air, the complexes separated out as crystals. The crystal were filtered off, washed with acetone and finally with ether and dried in vacuum.

The elemental analyses of complexes and other experimental methods used were same as in the earlier paper¹⁵. Results are reported in Tables 1-3.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) correspond to the general formula, $UO_2X_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$ ($X=Cl, Br, I, NO_3, NCS$ or CH_3COO) for the complexes. All the complexes were coloured, non-hygroscopic crystalline solids soluble in polar solvents and with the exception of $UO_2I_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$, they were stable in air. The latter complex decomposed slowly giving out iodine vapour. The electrical conductivity values $3.2-5.9 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ in nitrobenzene indicate the complexes as non-electrolytes. Molecular weights of the complexes determined cryoscopically in freezing nitrobenzene further confirm the monomeric nature of the complexes (Table 1).

In general, the ir spectra of the halo-complexes closely resemble each other, while those of the nitrate, thiocyanate and acetate complexes show extra bands due to the corresponding anionic species (Table 2). The strong $S=O$ stretching band in free non-coordinated DBzSO at $1032 cm^{-1}$ (Refs. 16, 17) were not observed in the ir spectra of the complexes $UO_2X_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$ wherein a new band in the region $960-970 cm^{-1}$ was observed. The $C-S$ stretching band of DBzSO at $682 cm^{-1}$ is shifted to a slightly higher wave number in the complexes. Such shift of the $S=O$ and of the $C-S$ bands are indicative of the decrease in the double bond character of the $S=O$ bond and on electron shift from the aryl group to the sulphur atom of the ligand. The ir data thus suggest coordination from the oxygen atom of the DBzSO^{16,17}. A very strong absorption attributed to phenyl-S stretch by previous workers¹⁸ has been identified at $1079 cm^{-1}$ in free DBzSO which does not suffer any significant change on complexation. It indicates the absence of coordination from the sulphur atom of the ligand. In the far-ir region, the ν_{U-O} bands are identified at $410-400 cm^{-1}$ region^{19,20}. In addition to these ligand vibration modes, ν_1 and ν_2 vibrations of the uranyl ion²¹ in

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF $UO_2X_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$ COMPLEXES IN NITROBENZENE

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_m $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Average mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)
	U	S	Anion		
$UO_2Cl_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	29.86 (29.71)	7.82 (7.99)	8.39 (8.86)	8.2	801 (786)
$UO_2Br_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	26.58 (26.74)	6.91 (7.19)	17.16 (17.97)	3.9	890 (859)
$UO_2I_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	23.87 (24.18)	6.34 (6.50)	24.91 (25.81)	5.9	984 (963)
$UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	27.54 (27.86)	7.91 (7.49)	—	3.6	854 (839)
$UO_2(NCS)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	27.80 (28.13)	14.98 (15.18)	18.17 (18.71)	4.2	846 (829)
$UO_2(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	27.76 (28.06)	7.34 (7.54)	—	4.7	848 (832)

TABLE 2—PERTINENT IR DATA (cm^{-1}), FORCE CONSTANTS, U-O BOND DISTANCE OF $DBzSO$ COMPLEXES OF UO_2X_2

Compd.	$\nu(\text{Phen-S})$	$\nu(S=O)$	$\nu(U-O)$	$\nu_1(U=O)$	$\nu_2(U=O)$	U-O force constant m dynes/A	Force constant due to interac- tion between bonds m dynes/A	U-O (calcd.) distance A
$DBzSO$	1 079s	1 082vs	—	—	—	—	—	—
$UO_2Cl_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	1 076m	960s	410m	890	920	6.763 2	-0.269 5	1.741 1
$UO_2Br_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	1 080m	965s	405m	835	930	6.879 8	-0.307 1	1.737 8
$UO_2I_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	1 075s, b	970s	400m	830	925	6.801 6	-0.307 8	1.740 5
$UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	1 072s	955s	407m	837	928	6.879 6	-0.275 9	1.737 8
$UO_2(NCS)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	1 080m	960s	405m	832	925	6.817 2	-0.292 1	1.739 9
$UO_2(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$	1 075m	970s	410m	825	920	6.724 2	-0.308 5	1.742 8

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, b=broad, sh=shoulder, v=very.

TABLE 3—THERMOANALYTICAL RESULTS OF $UO_2X_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$

X	Sample weight mg	Residual mass mg	Ligand's mass loss (%)				Residual (%)	
			170-230°		260-390°		610°	
			Theor. ^a	Exp.	Theor. ^b	Exp.	Theor. ^c	Exp.
Cl	29.64	11.11	43.07	44.61	57.42	59.12	85.08	87.48
Br	28.32	9.18	38.76	40.16	51.68	53.06	81.53	82.41
NO_3	25.42	8.62	40.39	41.98	53.86	54.98	82.86	83.91
NCS	27.16	9.23	40.78	42.16	54.37	55.96	83.17	83.98
CH_3COO	26.91	9.02	40.68	41.98	54.24	55.83	83.09	83.51

^a Calculated for loss of 1.5 mol of ligand.

^b Calculated for total loss of ligand.

^c Calculated as U_3O_8 .

their $UO_2X_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$ complexes are observed at 837-825 and 930-920 cm^{-1} , respectively.

In the $UO_2(NCS)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$ complex, the C-N and C-S stretching band appear at 2 050 and 800 cm^{-1} , respectively. On the basis of the high relative intensity of the C-N band, it may be concluded that the thiocyanate group is N-bonded^{22,23} to the UO_2^{II} ion. The two ir bands at $\sim 1 550$ and $1 475 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complex $UO_2(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$ is attributed to the anti-symmetric and the symmetric stretching vibration of COO^- group.

Examination of the ir spectra of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2DBzSO$ reveals the absence of ionic nitrate group²⁴. This is evident from the splitting of the ν_3 band at $\sim 1 360 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ of the ionic nitrates into ν_1 ($\sim 1 280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and ν_4 ($\sim 1 520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) in the

complex. The nitrate group in this complex appears to be bidentate since the ir bands due to this group occur almost in the same region as in case of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $K[UO_2(NO_3)_3]$ and other uranyl nitrate complexes containing bidentate nitrate group^{15,25}. Bands at $\sim 1 030$, and ~ 810 and $\sim 730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in this complex are assigned to ν_2 , ν_6 and ν_5 , ν_8 modes, respectively of the coordinated nitrate groups²⁶. Thus uranium appear 8-coordinated in this complex. Uranium was also found 8-coordinated in the complexes^{25,28}, $Rb[UO_2(NO_3)_3]$, $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot (Ph_3PO)_2$ and $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$. In all other uranium(VI) complexes of $DBzSO$, the coordination number of uranium was 6.

In the present studies, it has been observed that the ν_1 mode of the uranyl ion appears as of weak intensity and ν_8 mode strong intensity in the ir

spectra (Table 3). A group theoretical consideration²⁷ shows that a linear and symmetrical triatomic UO_2^{II} ion possessing $D_{\infty h}$ symmetry gives rise to three fundamental modes of vibrations. Wilson's G-F matrix method²⁸ has been used to determine the stretching and interaction force constants. The results are in turn used to calculate the U-O bond distance following Badger's formula²⁹. The force constants, bond distances and spectral data used herein are summarised in Table 2. It is apparent from the calculated data that the U-O bond length decreases with the increase in the value of symmetric stretching frequency (ν_1)³⁰. A plot of ($\nu_1 + \nu_3$) vs force constants gave a straight line with the increase in the symmetric stretching vibrations on complexation; the U-O force constant and the force constant due to the interaction between the bonds were also found to increase. Further, the U-O bonds distances in uranyl salts generally range from 1.60 to 1.92 Å depending on the nature of the equatorial ligands³¹. The calculated values of the U-O bond distances in the present complexes are close to 1.73 ± 0.01 Å.

The thermograms of the complexes indicate virtually no change in weight upto 170°. At 173-230°, a loss of 39-43% is observed which corresponds to 1.5 mole of the ligand DBzSO, followed by a further loss of 53-59% at 260-360° showing the complete loss of DBzSO molecules leaving a residue of UO_3 . The oxide U_3O_8 was finally formed at ~610°. Above this temperature there is no observable change in weight.

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References

1. J. GOPALAKRISHNAN and C. O. PATEL, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1968, **27**, 47b.
2. J. A. DAVIES, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1981, **24**, 115.
3. F. A. COTTON and R. FRANCIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 2986.
4. J. O. EDWARD and J. A. STRITAR, *Science*, 1963, **142**, 1651.
5. V. KRISHNAN and C. O. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 416.
6. V. KRISHNAN and C. O. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1965, **27**, 244.
7. S. M. SINITSYNA and N. M. SINITSYN, *Dokl. Chem.*, 1966, **166**, 467.
8. G. KAUFMANN and M. J. F. LEROY, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1966, 3770.
9. V. V. SAVANT and C. O. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 2919.
10. V. V. SAVANT and C. O. PATEL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1462.
11. P. A. VIGATO, U. CASELLATO and M. VIDALI, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1977, **107**, 61.
12. B. B. MISHRA, S. R. MOHANTY, N. V. V. S. MURTI and S. RAYCHAUDHRI, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1978, **28**, 275.
13. S. S. SANDHU and S. S. SANDHU, JR., *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **11**, 869.
14. N. V. SIDWICK, "The Chemical Elements and their Compounds", Oxford, London, 1950.
15. A. K. SRIVASTAVA, S. SHARMA and R. K. AGARWAL, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1992, **61**, 285.
16. T. N. SRIVASTAVA, N. BHAKRU and R. K. AGARWAL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 402.
17. R. K. AGARWAL, P. KUMAR and H. K. RAWAT, *Thermochem. Acta*, 1985, **88**, 897.
18. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. O. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 2nd. ed., Wiley, New York, 1967.
19. J. P. DAY and L. M. VERANZI, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1960, 1969.
20. J. R. FERRARO and A. WALKER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1966, **45**, 550.
21. L. CATTALINI, U. CROATTO, S. DEGETTO and E. TONDELLO, *Inorg. Chim. Acta Rev.*, 1971, **5**, 19.
22. Z. M. S. AL-HAZAZ, K. W. BAGNALL and D. BROWN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, **35**, 1501.
23. J. L. BURMEISTER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 205, 1968, **3**, 225.
24. B. M. GATEHOUSE, S. E. LIVINGSTONE and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4222.
25. G. TOPPING, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 1749.
26. R. K. AGARWAL, J. R. CHOPRA and S. C. RASTOGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 164.
27. V. K. RASTOGI, A. N. PANDEY, S. L. GUPTA and R. O. SAXENA, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1980, **18**, 379.
28. L. B. WILSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 1047, 1941, **9**, 76.
29. R. M. BADGER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1934, **2**, 128, 1935, **3**, 710.
30. C. L. GARGA, S. D. GUPTA and K. V. NARASIMHAN, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1970, **8**, 108.
31. W. H. ZACHARIASEN, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1954, **7**, 783.
32. J. I. BULLOCK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 2257.